

SHUKUR KHOLMIRZAYEV IS A LIVING WRITER

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ANNOTATION

Shukur Kholmirzayev's work is one of the brightest and meaningful pages of contemporary Uzbek literature. Shukur Kholmirzayev, who had a multifaceted talent, enriched the treasury of Uzbek literature by creating colorful works of art in various genres of literature. The article provides information about his colorful stories, journalistic articles, historical essays, realistic stories, and wonderful novels that he has taken a worthy place in modern literature.

KEY WORDS: *Uzbek literature, artistic skill, style, story genre, realistic spirit, high ideal stories, human relations, living writer.*

INTRODUCTION:

Shukur Kholmirzayev, the writer of Uzbekistan, who is in a living memory made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature of the 20th century. Shukur Xolmirzayev, a writer of Uzbekistan, was a winner of Uzbekistan's state , Oybek, Hamza, Termiziy and an order of cocktail fame rewards. Shukur Kholmirzayev was born in 1940 in Boysun district of Surkhandarya region. After graduating the school with honors, he entered Tashkent State University in 1956. Shukur Kholmirzayev remembers that he developed a passion for literature while studying at school. At the Faculty of Philology of Tashkent State University, this desire increases even more. In the same years, Shukur Kholmirzayev took his first steps in the field of artistic creation. Academician Matyakub Koshzhanov says about the writer's first work: "He was

sleeping in the mountain, wrapped in his winter fur like a polar bear. His neck was narrowly white. a paved path will pass."

MAIN PART:

The talented writer Shukur Kholmirzayev is one of the creators who has his own voice and style in modern Uzbek literature. He entered our literature in 1962 with the short story "White Horse". The story is written for children, it reflects the unique dreams and views of young people. Shukur Kholmirzayev has written many stories, short stories and novels in more than thirty years after publishing this story. It can be said without exaggeration that Shukur Kholmirzayev entered the literature like lightning, like a bright flame, the story "Who is not eighteen" has risen to the level of a guide for eighteen-year-olds. After reading this story, Odil Yakubov writes: "He details the image very darkly, as if he doesn't interfere. He works with paints, not with words, just like an artist and with a small brush. We don't read his works, as if or we watch it like a picture.

Continuing the traditions of his teacher, Shukur Kholmirzayev had a special attitude to literature and became famous as the author of high fiction stories. In an interview with journalist Tahir Yunus, he said: "Doctor Abdulla Kahhor was such a master. From his stories, it can be assumed that literature is a craft. I can't agree with that. On the contrary, I have a different opinion. Writing is not a craft, it is a destiny.

If you work on yourself, if you have talent, you can become a writer. I had to rewrite individual stories up to ten times, and it didn't always work." Constant, hard work on oneself, raising the level of skill quickly showed itself - Shukur Kholmirzayev to the famous writer and storyteller Of course, he also wrote novels, plays, essays, and novels. But stories brought him fame. Shukur Kholmirzayev reveals the lives of heroes with such attention and care, no matter what genre, what size, what work he creates. reveals every word, phrase, tool in the right scale, which indicates the realism of the whole creation.

It should be said that the color of Surkhandarya region (Surkhan), where he was born and raised, plays an important role in the formation of the writer's unique style. The reader feels the geographical climate, local customs, dialect, and even intonation of the inhabitants of Surkhan. At the same time, one can feel the character of Surkhandars - correctness, honesty, decency. The study of Shukur Kholmirzayev's work made it possible to identify another feature of his style: as a rule, the events described by him are dramatic, full of emotions, but the writer hides them, the reader must perceive them. According to literary critic U. Normatov, this image style "sometimes weakens the power of influence, the attractiveness of the image. After all, literature is art, it should be expressed."

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that Shukur Kholmirzayev follows the established tradition and has a real approach to everything depicted, including the hero. He is not a supporter of the position that a positive character should be distinguished by a pleasant appearance, and a negative one - on the contrary. No matter what the hero is, he has a special attitude towards it - he expresses it as it is in life.

Another characteristic feature of the writer's style is the use of scenery as an element describing the inner world of the hero. Not only landscape sketches, but also the skillful use of dialogic scenes serve as a means of characterization for the writer. His friends, relatives, and the literary community appreciate him as a tasteful, honest, proud, strong artistic thinking, honest, talented writer, possessor of unique skills, and a great writer. Shukur Kholmirzayev's 40-year creative cocktail is the result of searches, losses, entering and exiting the world's storytelling schools, and most importantly, lessons learned from his mistakes and experiences. We can say that the spiritual evolutionary growth of Shukur Kholmirzayev is also reflected in his works. That is probably why Shukur Kholmirzayev took a worthy place in Uzbek literature and gained fame as the author of highly ideological stories.

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